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Project management on adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization

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Abstract

The relevance of the studied problem is substantiated by the need for implementation of management of process of adaptation of young teachers for the general education organization and insufficient readiness of theoretical, substantial, technological, scientific, and methodical aspects of management of process of adaptation of young teachers in the course of pedagogical activity. In this regard, we reviewed development, approbation and management of the educational project on adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization in this article. Questions of definition and creation of organizational and pedagogical conditions of management of the educational project on adaptation of young teachers at school are considered. The efficiency of the created and introduced organizational and pedagogical conditions is considered by authors through a prism of key functional fields of project management. The purpose of article consists in the description of implementation of the project on adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization and experimental check of management efficiency of it based on the developed matrix of works on formation of organizational and pedagogical conditions. The main method of a research of this problem is the design allowing considering this problem as the process of purposeful and conscious project management on adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization.

Keywords: educational project; project management; organizational and pedagogical conditions; adaptation of young teachers.

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Introduction

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Realization of an order of the President of the Russian Federation to provide formation of the national system of teacher's growth directed to establishment for pedagogical workers of levels of proficiency in professional competences is carried out through creation of a system of incentives for the professional growth of teachers on the basis of all-federal (objective and independent) estimates of the level of the necessary qualification of teachers offered in model of a national system of teacher's growth. At the expense of the listed mechanisms, growth of level of proficiency in professional competences of teachers is supposed.

In the draft of the professional standard of the teacher, developed taking into account the system of incentives of professional growth of teachers, it is supposed that introduction of the new professional standard will cause the change of standards of its preparation and retraining of teachers in the higher school and in training centers.

Modern society places great demands on school education and on teachers; teachers have to have new pedagogical thinking and to be capable to become active participants of innovative processes in education. The teacher has to have a high level of the academic knowledge of the chosen specialty, all-pedagogical and methodic-technological culture. The teacher has to be able culturally, communicate unostentatiously with pupils based on the subject and subject relations, build the relations with colleagues and higher structures based on friendship, cooperation, mutual aid (Dolgova, Melnik, & Motorina, 2015).

Now the training of future teachers is carried out according to the requirements of the federal state educational standards of the higher education where results of training conform to this standard, but only partially satisfy the generalized labor functions and characteristics of the labor functions shown in the professional standard of the teacher.

Purpose and objectives of the study

We set to review the development, approbation, and management of the educational projects on adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization. We set to answer the questions of definition and creation of organizational and pedagogical conditions of management of the educational project on the adaptation of young teachers at school.

Literature review

Empirical researches (Chernikova, 2014) confirm the fact that most of the young teachers are not able to apply the theoretical knowledge gained in higher education institution in practice, experience difficulties in design, organizing, and communicative activity, problems in the organization of the after-hour work and cooperation with families of pupils.

Because of the carried-out analysis of standard and legal documentation in education, we revealed the following contradictions (1) between training of young teachers according to federal state educational standard of the higher education in the Pedagogical education direction and partial compliance to requirements of the professional standard imposed to qualification of the teacher (Petrenko, 2017); (2) between need of providing the industry with the highly qualified administrative and pedagogical personnel ready to activity in the conditions of modernization of education and insufficient professional and pedagogical training of university graduates for implementation of the practical-focused activity (Shevchenko, 2014).

On the solution of the revealed problems of inconsistency of federal state educational standard of the higher education on the Pedagogical education direction and the professional standard of the teacher; insufficient providing the industry with the highly qualified administrative and pedagogical personnel having the high

level of professional readiness for activity in the conditions of modernization of education the effective administrative project on adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization is directed.

In the course of studying of literature on a subject of research, theoretic-methodological bases of the organizational and pedagogical conditions influencing the process of management of the project on the adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization are revealed.

We consider process of social and professional adaptation of the teacher as the process of interaction of the personality and during which professional environment of the development of the purposes, values, and norms of professional activity caused by a combination of the external and internal factors providing optimum performance and development of the individual in a profession is carried out.

Special attention is paid to pedagogical mentoring and the forms of individual and collective mentoring. Both individual and collective forms of mentoring help young teachers to find own forms of work in a creative search (Ippolitova, 2012).

Successful adaptation of the young teacher is also promoted by improvement of social conditions, an increase in its living standards; improvement of labor organization in the general education organization and the solution of a question of free time of the teacher (labor division, mutual aid, the lesson schedule, etc.); style of the management; the help rendered to the young teacher from pedagogical collective; salary level, etc.

As a result, we suggest the system of actions of the project on the adaptation of young teachers to divide in the general education organization into groups:

- 1) Program for methodical maintenance (a program of mentoring).
- 2) Program of actions for improvement of the social and psychological climate.
- 3) Methods of involvement and motivation of human resources.
- 4) Organizational and pedagogical conditions of project management on the adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization.

We believe that organizational and pedagogical conditions represent a whole, acting as its equivalent parts. Organizational conditions carry out the support of an opportunity and maintenance of realization of pedagogical conditions, i.e. act as the spatial environment for the educational environment. Thus, we will understand characteristic of a pedagogical system reflecting the set of potential opportunities of the spatial and educational environment which realization will provide the ordered and directed effective functioning and also development of a pedagogical system as organizational and pedagogical conditions.

Based on the analysis of the key directions in the management of the educational project and based on the carried-out analysis of references pedagogical conditions of project management on the adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization are allocated: management of subject domain of the project, human resource management in the project, management of communications.

Selection of organizational and pedagogical conditions is necessary for the achievement of the goal of the project on the adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization; it is development, introduction, and realization of a complex of the actions providing successful adaptation of young teachers in the educational institution.

Implementation of the project on the adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization depends on the creation of organizational and pedagogical conditions which structure includes psychology and pedagogical, personnel, material technical and financial conditions. Proceeding from above told, it is possible to draw a conclusion that organizational and pedagogical conditions, it is necessary to form on

stages initiation, planning, the organization and control, the analysis and regulation, closing in order that process of management of the project went effectively.

Methodology

Methodological bases include (1) competence-based approach in modernization of professional education; (2) the design approach, fundamental provisions opening questions of the theory and practice of management of educational projects; (3) Features of project management in the general education organizations; (4) standards of International Association of project management (PMA, IPMA).

Research methods are (1) theoretical: analysis of scientific literature, standard and legal documentation, qualitative analysis of results; (2) empirical: questioning, pedagogical experiment, SWOT analysis; (3) statistical: method of mathematical statistics.

The skilled and experimental base of research was Municipal state general education establishment high comprehensive school No. 6 of the city of Kirovo-Chepetsk.

Results

The research of a problem was carried out in three steps. At the first stage, the theoretical analysis of scientific literature, standard and legal documentation, practical experience in a context of researches of a problem is carried out. The scientific device of research is specified. Purposes, hypotheses, tasks, the concept of the project on the adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization were formulated. At the second stage, development and approbation of the "Adaptation of Young Teachers in the General Education Organization" project was carried out; the pedagogical experiment was performed. At the third stage, results of empirical research are processed and analyzed, assessment of efficiency of organizational and pedagogical conditions of project management "Adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization" is carried out; conclusions are formulated.

Subject group	Management Team				
	Initiation	Planning	Organization and control	Analysis and regulation	Completion
1	2	3	4	5	6
Management of subject domains of the project	1	2	3	4	5
	Determination of content	Development of the Charter of the project	Management on milestones	Preparation of the report on workflow	End of the project or phase
	Determination of criteria of success and failures	Determination of the structure of decomposition of works of WBS	Management of contents of the project	Comparison of the report with the plan	Preservation of the accumulated experience
	Definition of works		Control of design activity		
	Approbation of results		Control of changes		
	6	7	8	9	10

Management of cost and financing	Cost estimation	Budget making	Control of expenses on the estimate	Control of cost, comparison with the plan	Preparation of the report on the performance of work
Management of temporary parameters	11	12	13	14	15
	Determination of the sequence of works	Drawing up network schedule (chart Ganta)	Control of the schedule	Control of the schedule	Preparation of the report on the performed works
	Assessment of duration of works				
Development of the schedule					
Risk management	16	17	18	19	20
	Identification of risks	Definition of measures of prevention and response to risks	Risk management	Monitoring and control over risks	Preparation of the report on the performance of work
Risk assessment					
Management of communications	21	22	23	24	25
	Determination of structure of interested persons	Planning of communications	Dissemination of information	Preparation of the reporting under project milestones	Preparation of the report on performance of work
			Management of interested persons of the project		
Management of communications					
Management of human resources	26	27	28	29	30
	Assessment of resources of the project	Drawing up a matrix of responsibility	Formation of a team of the project	Preparation of the report on results of management of human resources	Preparation of the report on the performance of work
Determination of the organizational structure of the project	Management of a team of the project		Comparison of the report with the plan		

Quality management	31	32	33	34	35
	Determination of criteria of success and failures of the project	Planning of quality	Quality assurance Quality control	Quality control	Preparation of the report on the performance of work

Table 1. Classification of processes of design management-by-management and subject teams

Formation of personnel conditions	Formation of psychology and pedagogical conditions	Formation of material conditions	Formation of financial conditions
Development of provision on mentoring	Development and approval of Regulations of work of Club of the young teacher	Acquisition of the MFP and computer, connection it to network of local school network, installation of the necessary software and in the 407th office	Drawing up estimate of the "Adaptation of Young Teachers in the General Education Organization" project
Development of the scheduled plan of certification of young teachers.	Drawing up the list of the young teachers needing improvement of housing conditions. Execution of the petition in administration of the municipal unit "City of Kirovo-Chepetsk" of the Kirov region for granting office housing to young teachers	Equipment of a computer class 10 computers, projector and MFP	Conclusion of agreement with branch of Kirovo-Chepetsk Chemical Works of URALCHEM in the city of Kirovo-Chepetsk about a charitable gift of money of 09.01.2018, the cooperation agreement (partnership) of the agreement with branch of Kirovo-Chepetsk Chemical Works of URALCHEM in the city of Kirovo-Chepetsk of 09.01.2018
Scheduling of work of the regional innovative platform "Formation of Universal Educational Actions in the conditions of Realization of System	Introduction of amendments to the Provision on compensation in connection with increase in a basic salary of pedagogical workers to 11163 rubles		Development and adoption of the Provision on material stimulation of pedagogical workers and Provision on compensation of employees of Local state educational institution of

and Approach"	Activity			high comprehensive school No. 6 of the city of Kirovo-Chepetsk of the Kirov region
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Table 2. *Matrix of works on the formation of organizational and pedagogical conditions*

The effective management of the developed and approved project on the adaptation of young teachers was checked by means of the analysis of project management "Adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization".

The analysis was carried out leaning on a design triangle and included three stages.

The first stage is the analysis of the management of temporary parameters was carried out on key milestones. All works are performed in time or have insignificant deviations within the norm.

The second stage is carrying out the analysis of the management of cost and financing of the project. The analysis "plan fact" of project cost for a method of the mastered volume showed that the actual cost of the performed works is lower planned, therefore, economic expense of budgetary funds of the project is observed.

At the third stage, earlier specified criteria of success and failures of the project we carried out the analysis of quality management of the project: four criteria are in fully executed from five criteria of success: the program of actions is approved, local acts are adopted, methodical training of young teachers is organized, growth of quality of training of students at young teachers is observed, young teachers are provided with office housing.

The analysis of project management "Adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization" allowed drawing the following conclusions: (1) all works of the project are performed in time and deviations on periods are in norm limits; (2) the actual cost of the performed works of the project is not beyond the planned estimate and the selected local authority budget; (3) the quality of the provided services estimated by criteria of success and failures conforms to requirements of the customer of the project.

Discussion

Studying of psychology and pedagogical literature allows to state lack of the special researches devoted to a problem of management of the process of adaptation of young teachers in the course of pedagogical activity. However, the questions concerning the adaptation of the young teacher, its factors of the strategy were considered by a number of researchers.

Adaptation of the young specialist to conditions of the modern school is considered in the research by Zubtsova (2011). The author established that traditional forms of organizational and pedagogical activity began to slow down the process of updating of comprehensive school. Besides the frequent removability of teachers, the system of work of each educational institution negatively influences. Improvement of the process of training of future teachers demands the creation of new organizational and pedagogical systems of the introduction of effective methods and forms of education, which have an impact on the formation of the expert of the top skills in the conditions of interaction and continuity of all links of a system of vocational training. One of such processes is a professional and pedagogical adaptation of students, which result, has to be a high level of professional readiness, the desire of graduates to work at school.

The set of conditions of successful adaptation can be expressed in the following:

- Existence of a healthy moral and psychological climate;
- Positive relation and interest of young specialists in pedagogical activity;

- Satisfaction with domestic conditions;
- Creation of the corresponding conditions and labor organization;
- Satisfaction with the help rendered by a pedagogical collective in the formation of experience of the beginning teacher. Components of professional adaptation of the teacher: career guidance of school students, selection of entrants, high school training, training, experience formation, social protection of the teacher (Zubtsova, 2013).

Questions of tutor maintenance of adaptation of the young teacher to conditions of college devoted works as Vasilyeva (2013). Proceeding from the analysis of the received results, the researcher notes the complexity of young teachers at the establishment of contact with students. To them it is difficult for students of the college to impart skills of professional activity; it is difficult to understand innovative trends of development of professional education, to adapt in collective. Therefore, additional knowledge in the field of pedagogical, age and social psychology, a technique of teaching subject matters, use of innovative methods and forms of carrying out a theoretical and practical training is necessary for young teachers up to standard to provide an educational process in groups of primary and secondary professional education. In this regard, support of all services of college is necessary for the beginning teacher: scientific and methodical, psychological, etc. During tutor maintenance, the individual trajectory of development of the young teacher according to his competences and individual and personal features is built.

Factors of social and psychological adaptation of young teachers in detail are considered by Sokolova and Rudenko (2018). Conducting empirical researches of this problem scientist defined a vital issue, a pedagogical profession, characteristic of beginners. This problem is fixing of young teachers at school, the major condition that there is their social and psychological adaptation in the educational organization. Every fifth teacher is in schools of the country at a stage of social and psychological adaptation to professional activity. Its success or not success in many respects is explained by the fact that the beginning teacher is obliged to carry out the same amount of works, as other members of the pedagogical collective, but the lack of experience does not allow university graduates to work on an equal basis with colleagues. The importance of adaptation is that in the course of it the young teacher has satisfaction with the work that is an important condition of further professional growth. Withdrawal from a profession turns out to be a consequence of professional dissatisfaction: in 1-2 years of 44% from among unsatisfied leave pedagogical work while among that only 14% are satisfied with the beginning of a way.

Sivrikova and Chernikova (2018) studied the strategy of adaptation of young teachers of comprehensive schools. Therefore, based on the researches authors concluded that the period of adaptation of the young specialist to work lasts on average from 3 to 5 years. The greatest difficulties cause the first weeks and months of work, but not they become the reasons of the crisis phenomena. The success of the social and psychological adaptation of the teacher at school depends on the ability of the person to effectively use the strategy of behavior directed to overcoming difficult life situations. Studying ways of overcoming difficulties acquires special relevance when the teacher for the first time starts the independent professional activity.

The group of scientists of the Moscow state psychology and pedagogical university (Andrushchenko et al., 2017) conducts psychology and pedagogical researches of a problem of professional adaptation of young teachers. From the point of view of the authors, social and professional support of young teachers is one of the priority directions in the educational policy of the majority of developed countries. Scientists' analyses examples of the introduction of the comprehensive programs of adaptation directed to the involvement of young teachers in a profession, and to their deduction in it in England, Germany, Canada, the USA and New

Zealand are most known. As a result, they concluded that programs for professional adaptation of young teachers in various combinations include measures for entry into a profession, certifications, social and psychological support. The group of authors allocated two levels of adaptation of the young specialist:

- professional, covering features of the organization, contents, and technology of professional activity;
- social and psychological, directly connected with entry into a certain organization, i.e. “adaptation to the collective, to its traditions, style of work of heads, features of the interpersonal relations in collective, as the inclusion of the worker in collective as equal, accepted by all his members means”.

According to the foreign researches, the more various forms of adaptation of young teachers are used in the educational organization, the more young teachers remain to work in it. Most often adaptation of young teachers consists in interaction with the representative of administration and the mentor. The level of confidence of most young teachers at school in such cases is higher than at those schools where the beginning teachers do not get any support, but the difference is not too essential. Among young teachers who received the multi-component help from school (except the listed above adaptation forms, they participated in seminars for the beginning teachers, could plan the program of carrying out lessons together with experienced teachers, had the reduced academic load, etc.), it is twice more of those who continued to work at this school further, than among the beginning teachers not getting any support.

The problem of adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization proves the relevance of our research.

The conducted research allowed drawing the following conclusions. Process of social and professional adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization has the features. Successful adaptation of the young teacher is promoted: improvement of social conditions, increase in its living standards; improvement of labor organization in the general education organization and the solution of a question of free time of the teacher; the help tends to the young teacher from the pedagogical collective. Then, organizational and pedagogical conditions of effective management of the project on the adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization which structure includes psychology and pedagogical, personnel, material technical and financial conditions are in detail opened and listed. In general, selection of organizational and pedagogical conditions was necessary for achievement of the goal of the project on adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization – it is development, introduction, and realization of a complex of the actions providing successful adaptation of young teachers in educational institution. Also, the "Adaptation of Young Teachers in the General Education Organization" project was developed and approved. Besides, the effective management of the educational project "Adaptation of Young Teachers in the General Education Organization" was estimated based on the analysis of the management of the educational project "Adaptation of Young Teachers in the General Education Organization".

In general, having generalized all analyses data, we draw a conclusion that control of the educational project "Adaptation of Young Teachers in the General Education Organization" was exercised effectively on all indicators from the specified directions. Studying of psychology and pedagogical literature allows to state lack of the special researches devoted to a problem of management of the process of adaptation of young teachers in the course of pedagogical activity.

Conclusion

During the research on project management on adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization it was established that the leading factors of adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization are improvement of social conditions, increase in its living standards; improvement of labor organization in the general education organization; the help rendered to the young teacher from pedagogical collective. It is also the implementation of the project on the adaptation of young teachers in the general education organization depends on the creation of organizational and pedagogical conditions which structure includes psychology and pedagogical, personnel, material technical and financial conditions. For the creation of necessary organizational and pedagogical conditions in the general education organization, it is required to approach the process of adaptation of young teachers as to project management and to exercise it according to stages project management initiation, planning, the organization and control, the analysis and regulation, closing. Not last is effective management of the developed and approved the project on the adaptation of young teachers is checked by means of the analysis of the management of the educational project "Adaptation of Young Teachers in the General Education Organization".

The reliability and validity of research are provided with the adequacy of the applied methods for assessment of effective management of the "Adaptation of Young Teachers in the General Education Organization" project. The effective management of the "Adaptation of Young Teachers in the General Education Organization" project is defined according to a design triangle: (1) implementation of the analysis of management of temporary parameters; (2) carrying out analysis of management of cost and financing of the project; (3) implementation of the analysis of quality management of the project.

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